

TARGETED PLANNING OF BUDGET EXPENDITURES AND IMPACT ON SOCIAL POLICY

Oralov Nurbek Abdukarimovich

Academy of Banking and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Jumaniyazov Inomjon Turayevich

PhD., Associate professor TSUE

Annotation. *The article underscores the pivotal role of social security in the fabric of state and societal life, highlighting its dependence on the country's economic development and social policies. Uzbekistan aims to build a robust social state, focusing on improving living conditions, education, healthcare, culture, and sports. Significant strides have been made in the past seven years, notably in expanding pre-school education coverage, increasing school capacity, and fostering private sector involvement in education and healthcare. Social security needs, rooted in the emergence of society, encompass support for children, the elderly, disabled, orphans, and temporarily or permanently disadvantaged individuals. Economic development and complex social relations further necessitate social assistance for the unemployed and economically disadvantaged.*

Key words: *Social security, state and society, economic development, social policy, social state, uzbekistan, education, healthcare.*

Social security is always central and decisive in the life of the state and society took the place. Citizens living in the country of their life activities to the services of the social security system at certain stages and in special cases needs arise. Its status is at the level of the country's economic development, to the social policy carried out in the country, as well as to workers and to the social condition of the strata of the population who do not work for certain reasons depends.

Building a social state in Uzbekistan is a strategic goal. All measures are being taken to create suitable conditions for the life of the population, to develop education, healthcare, culture and sports.

In the last seven years, coverage in pre-school education has increased from 27 percent to 74 percent. New schools were built and additional 700,000 student places were created. Presidential schools were established, specialized schools increased. The number of higher educational institutions has exceeded 200, and the coverage has reached 42%. In education and medicine, a wide path has been opened to the private sector, and a desire for quality has appeared.¹

The need for social security was born with the emergence of society. Any in society - regardless of its economic and political structure - depends on them able to earn a living due to unforeseen circumstances there will be categories of population that are not. To them, first of all, children and the elderly, disabled, orphans, single citizens. In addition to social assistance people who have temporarily or permanently lost the ranks of the needy can fill. As society develops and social relations become more complex among citizens in need of social assistance due to economic reasons

¹ On February 5, under the chairmanship of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a video selector meeting was held to discuss priority tasks in the social sphere.

the unemployed, the poor, as well as material from high rates of inflation including those whose conditions have worsened. Citizens of this category socially support and concentration of certain financial resources at the community level requires mobilization for social security purposes.

State budget expenditures for 2024 are planned in the amount of 312 trillion 921 billion soums, said Erkin Gadoyev, chairman of the Senate Budget and Economic Reforms Committee. - It should be noted that in the current year's budget, social sector expenses make up a significant share. More than 48 percent of expenses or 151.5 trillion soums will be directed to the social sector

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Figure 1. Composition of social expenditure, forecast for 2024, billion soums.²

The National Social Protection Agency was established under the President. It was created in order to ensure the rights of citizens regarding social protection and to fundamentally improve the quality of social services.

The agency is the authorized state body for the development and implementation of the unified state policy in the field of social protection of the population and provision of social services. It performs its activities independently of other state bodies and organizations and their officials.³

Phased implementation is planned until 2026 measures to strengthen the social protection system and mechanisms:

² <https://openbudget.uz>

³ <https://www.gazeta.uz>

- system of state social assistance through social contracts create;
- local in the provision of state social assistance and services mechanism of social work at the level (based on the principle of "neighbourhood") gradual introduction;
- all orphans and homeless children left without parental care housing provision;
- "Unified register of social protection" information system of the population all socially vulnerable groups and those who are shown to them to a single database for all social assistance and services rotate.

In recent years, many works have been carried out in the social sphere in our country. In particular, the establishment of the "Single Register of Social Protection" is a clear example of this. Through the unified social register, the efficiency of budget funds and the consideration of every citizen in need of social protection in the country are ensured.

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